

STUDY OF THE INFLUENCE OF ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS ON THE FORMATION OF DIABETES MELLITUS AND THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ART THERAPY IN CHILDREN WITH TYPE I DIABETES MELLITUS, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT COPING STRATEGIES

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of the effectiveness of modern art technologies in adolescents with diabetes mellitus, reveals the influence of diabetes mellitus on the clinical manifestations of affective disorders, establishes periods of low mood with internal tension, daily mood fluctuations, decreased motivational activity, deterioration of intra-family relationships against the background of emotional changes in children. The results obtained will make it possible to identify important personal targets of psychotherapeutic and psychocorrectional work with children prone to the development of anxiety-depressive and phobic symptoms.*

Key words: *environmental factors, art therapy, diabetes mellitus, coping strategies, children, anxiety disorders, emotional disorders, depression.*

Introduction. The combination of environmental and genetic variables leads to the development of type 1 diabetes mellitus (DM1). A complicated combination of genetic predisposition and environmental circumstances determines the likelihood of acquiring DM1. As skin UV irradiation is the primary source of vitamin D, the length of sunny days directly affects vitamin D availability. Numerous investigations have demonstrated a strong negative feedback loop between the amount of time spent exposed to ambient UV light and the incidence of DM1. According to recent research, which looked at how 72 different countries' climates affected the development of DM1, DM1 was more common in northern regions with shorter sun exposure times. There were also reports of vitamin D insufficiency among the younger population. There might be some benefits to giving vitamin D in these areas in addition. As of right now, the protective mechanism of UV exposure against the chance of acquiring DM1 remains unclear. This could be caused by distinct immunoregulatory effects as well as the control of vitamin D synthesis. It is still up for debate whether nitrates, nitrites, and nitrosamines might be harmful to pancreatic cells. For children who are genetically prone to DM1, exposure to chemically harmful chemicals in food or water can trigger autoimmune responses that ultimately result in the death of pancreatic islet cells. There may be a connection between DM1 and water that contains nitrates, nitrites, or nitrosamines, according to certain indirect environmental data. Studies on the environment looking at the connection between nitrate, nitrite, and nitrosamine exposure in food and drinking water and the development of DM1 found that patients with maximum nitrate levels of more than 40–80 mg/l had an increased risk of developing DM1, while regions with nitrate levels in drinking water less than 25 mg/l generally had no risk at all. The possible diabetogenic impact of nitrite and nitrosamines is not well-documented in experiments, and it is typically linked to higher concentrations that are outside of tolerable bounds [14]. To fully understand the potentially detrimental impact of exposure to nitrate-containing chemicals on the likelihood of developing DM1, more research is required. Due to the high prevalence of diabetes mellitus in children and the lack of understanding regarding many of its clinical and psychological components, this study is pertinent [3,9]. Young people with diabetes who have just received a diagnosis require

specialized educational and psychological assistance. This group of patients receives psychotherapeutic assistance, which helps to build a partnership between the psychologist and the patient. For more thorough and effective treatment, early psychodiagnostics and psychocorrection of disorders pertaining to the anxiety-depressive and phobic spectrum of the neurotic level are required [2,4,8]. In association with the rising advance in pharmacotherapy, the issues of an coordinates approach to the treatment and organization of psychosocial recovery, social adjustment and adjustment of anxiety-phobic and depressive indications in children and youths gotten to be as important as conceivable [1,5,7]. The investigation of scholarly sources uncovered deficiently information of the impact of sort 1 diabetes mellitus on the psychoemotional state of school-age youths and the plausibility of craftsmanship treatment for patients with a psychosomatic profile, which is why this consider is due. The issue of overcoming unpleasant and basic circumstances by a individual is examined by researchers in different areas of information: science, pharmaceutical, psychophysiology, brain research, and as of now remains one of the foremost significant in science. Maintained intrigued in this issue is due to the expanded negative affect of common, natural, social and other unfavorable conditions on the person. In this respect, the consider of mental ways of adapting with stretch as a figure of successful human adjustment within the cutting-edge world is of specific significance (L.I. Antsyferova, F.B. Berezin, V.A. Bodrov, B.P. Kaznacheev, A.R. Kudashev, V.I. Medvedev, F.Z. Meerson, A.A. Rean, M.S. Yanitsky, etc.). The research notes that unusualness and vulnerability, which are the most characteristics of extraordinary circumstances, have the foremost unpleasant impact on the psychophysical and utilitarian state of a individual. It is known that within the nearness of extraordinary human presentation, the highlights of a person's adapting procedures to a great extent decide the results of traumatic push: different shapes of identity disarrange are related either with inadequately adapting assets or with an abundance of maladapting push variables [6]. The reason of the think about the impact of natural variables on the arrangement of diabetes mellitus and the adequacy of craftsmanship treatment in adolescents with sort I diabetes mellitus, taking under consideration the mechanisms of adapting behavior to optimize mental, psychocorrective and helpful mental care.

Materials and methjds. The of inquire about. 110 children of senior school age with a confirmed conclusion of sort I diabetes were inspected. The strategy of deciding adapting methodologies for school-age children created by I.M. Nikolskaya and R.M. Granovskaya was utilized. To diminish psychoemotional changes in teenagers, bunch and person classes were conducted by restorative clinicians and psychotherapists for 3 months concurring to a uncommonly created recovery program utilizing present day craftsmanship advances. The diagnosis of diabetes mellitus was confirmed agreeing to the demonstrative criteria of ICD-10. A extraordinarily outlined examination card made by the staff of the Division of Psychiatry alongside clinical and social analysts contained a list of mental test questions to identify risk variables for the arrangement of endocrinological infections, taking under consideration coping methodologies and the seriousness of psychoemotional clutters. The dispersion by clinical bunches, taking under consideration the endocrinological determination, was as takes after 37 (46.3% of the consider cases) patients with mellow DM, 34 (42.5% of the ponder cases) patients with direct DM; 9 (11.2% of the think about cases) patients with serious DM. The normal age of the patients was 14.8 ± 1.7 a long time. The share of young ladies is 45%, boys – 55%. At the starting organize of the think about, clinical and psychopathological strategies by addressing, watching patients and collecting anamnestic data from guardians and relatives uncovered clinical variations of full of feeling

disarranges in young people, among which depressive disarranges were recognized in 96.6% of young people, uneasiness disarranges in 86.1% of youths, dysphoric – in 28.6%, phobic – in 54.7% of the inspected patients. At the following organize of the ponder, utilizing the eight Lusher color tests, changes within the psycho-emotional circle of the inspected patients were explored, which decided that 96.6% of the inspected teenagers appeared signs of depressive disorder of the psychotic enlist of gentle or moderate clinical appearances. Youths with hyperglycemia created dysphoric states, rather long periods of moo disposition with inside pressure, day by day disposition vacillations, diminished motivational activity, and disintegration of intra-family connections. Against the foundation of depressive clutters, adolescents' school execution essentially decreased (58%), need of crave to proceed their thinks about (25%), clashes with peers and behavioral clutters showed up (60%), self-destructive considerations and inclinations (15%). Within the inspected gather, amid testing utilizing the G.V. test. Rezyapkina uncovered the nearness of uneasiness disarranges of varying severity in young people, among them the nearness of appearances of direct uneasiness (67.8%) was famous, in 20.7% of the subjects – without clinically critical uneasiness and in 11.5% of young people – articulated uneasiness was noted. Anxiety expanded basically within the evening and was related with stresses around a physical illness. Uneasiness was going with by the arrangement of gentle and moderate depressive clutters, which permits us to define the concept of comorbidity of emotional clutters and sort I diabetes mellitus. The structure of full of feeling disarranges shifted depending on the organize and seriousness of diabetes mellitus. At the organize of tall hyperglycemia, 26 youths (86%) had the taking after side effects anxiety-phobic clutters, affective fluctuations, passionate lability with crabbiness. In 75% of cases, side effects of the depressive enroll were the first clinical signs of an worsening of the illness. Youths had reasonably long periods of asthenic states with inside pressure (23%), a feeling of threatening vibe from others and tall uneasiness (36%), episodes of unmotivated animosity (27%), over the top fears (16%). Dysthymia was watched in 100% of cases. As a result of changes within the enthusiastic state of youths, self-esteem essentially diminished (77%), push resistance to outside components was impeded (65%), a propensity to autism and confinement (70%), self-destructive eagerly and articulations (15%) were shaped. The instruments of mental assurance and styles of maladaptive behavior were decided utilizing adapting techniques for school-age children created by I.M. Nikolskaya and R.M. Granovskaya, who uncovered that forceful and angry behavioral responses are characteristic of patients with this psychosomatic pathology.

Conclusion. Hence, the specificity of the seriousness of the sorts of mental assurance is decided, which comprises within the favored utilize of defensive components for children with diabetes "dissent", "uprooting", "recompense", "receptive instruction" and adapting procedures "amusement and physical unwinding"; the relationship between behavioral characteristics and mental assurance, characterizing their defensive behavior as damaging and maladaptive. The viability of craftsmanship treatment in teenagers with diabetes mellitus has been set up as a strategy that decreases the level of misery and uneasiness, normalizes the psycho-emotional state and shapes versatile, stress-coping behavior.

1. The impact of sort I diabetes mellitus on the arrangement of psycho-emotional clutters in tall school children has been uncovered, uneasiness and depressive disarrange are watched to a more prominent degree, and phobic and dysphoric indications are enlisted to a lesser degree in patients.
2. It has been set up that with the irritation of the clinical signs of diabetes mellitus, the heightened

of individual and receptive uneasiness in children and teenagers advances, coming to greatest values with tall rates of hyperglycemia.

3. It was decided that within the handle of comparative investigate in children with DM, for the primary time, a more noteworthy seriousness was found:

uneasiness in a family circumstance; baffling responses intropunitive and focused on settling the circumstance; the utilize of coping strategies "crying, pitiful", "I apologize or I tell the truth", "I think around it" and their evaluation how to assist; intrapersonal clashes between the require for accomplishment and the fear of disappointment, the require for speedy accomplishments and need of capacity to exertion and tirelessness, endowed assignments and openings

4. The specificity of the seriousness of the sorts of mental security has been established, which comprises within the favored utilize of children with DM of security components "refusal", "uprooting", "recompense", "receptive instruction" and adapting procedures "excitement and physical unwinding"; the relationship between behavioral characteristics and mental assurance, characterizing their defensive behavior as dangerous and maladaptive.

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